

Exfoliation of Ti_3AlC_2 and Photocatalytical Application of MXene/ZnO composites

M. A. Patil¹ G.H. Sonawane¹

Kisan Arts, Commerce and Science College, Parola Dist Jalgaon (M.S.), India.

mayur.patil349@gmail.com

Abstract:-The intriguing features of MXene, a novel family of two-dimensional materials, include strong surface area, negative zeta potential, metallic conductivity, and electric conductivity. The majority of MXene are currently only successfully prepared by exfoliating MAX with high concentration hydrofluoric acids. In this study, the 2D Ti_3C_2 with large interplanar spacing was successfully achieved by alkali mixture of NaF and HCl, in single process. The morphology and structure of prepared sample characterized by XRD and SEM. This work presents a safely effective route to synthesize the 2D Ti_3C_2 . Fabrication of ZnO/MXene composites by a facile chemical method. Under UV irradiation, Rhodamine B was degraded by composites within 15 min and retained photo-catalytical efficiency after 5 cycles. Therefore ZnO/MXene composites can be regarded as an effective candidate for waste water treatment and environmental protection.

Keyword:- MAX phases, MXene, ZnO, Rhodamine B

1.Introduction:-Due to the discovery of graphene in 2004[1-3], 2D materials have attracted researcher interest. Owing to the reduction of the dimension and size, two-dimensional materials have exhibited many intriguing properties that are not found in their bulk counterparts, holding tremendous promise for a host of applications ranging from electronics[4-6] and optoelectronic device[7, 8], photocatalysis[9, 10] to electrochemical catalysis[11, 12]. In recent years, with great advances in the synthetic techniques, more 2D materials beyond graphene have been successfully produced such as silicene[12], silica glass[13], molybdenum disulfide[14, 15], germanene[16, 17], stannene[18], phosphorene[19]. Among them, a newly discovered large family of 2D large family of transitional metal carbide/ nitride or carbonitride called "MXene"[20], is rapidly rising star. These novel materials are produced from MAX phases with selective removal of A layers using etchants without destroying M-X bonds because the M-X bonds are much stronger than the M-A bonds[21]. MAX phases are

layered ternary compound with general formula of $M_{n+1}AX_n$ ($n=1,2,3$), where M represents early transition d block transition elements, A is predominately IIIA or IV A group element, and X is either C or N, MAX phases possess hexagonal layered structure in which $M_{n+1}X_n$ units and A layers are alternatively stacked. After the exfoliation resulting surface of MXene are terminated with other groups, such as -F, -OH and -O[22]. So, the MXene represents as $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, Where T is the surface terminal groups depends upon etchants solution and condition. Experimentally, the proportions of different functional groups on the MXene surface are uncertain. In case of hydrothermal or electrochemical etching methods absence of terminal functional groups and represented as $M_{n+1}X_n$ such as Ti_3C_2 [23]. Most of MXene shows metallic behavior exhibiting electronic conductivity higher than all other solution possessed 2D materials. These materials have shown significant promise in variety of applications including electrochemical energy storage[24], electromagnetic interference shielding[25], gas sensing[26], and many other. In particular, the good flexibility of MXene make easy to form composite with other materials, which provide an opportunity of integrating the outstanding properties of different materials in a complementary way. MXene also has exceptional capacity to transport photogenerated electron from closely coupled semiconductor photocatalyst and suppress the recombination of electron hole pairs[27]. However, MXene based photocatalyst system with more efficient for removal of water pollutants is still needed to develop.

ZnO is widely applied semiconductor photocatalyst in pollutants removal including heavy metal ions[28] and organic contaminants[29], and it has a strong oxidation capacity and a wide band gap (~ 3.3 eV)[30] because its valence band is sufficiently to generate hydroxy radicals[31]. On the other hand, ZnO shows fast recombination of electron hole pairs[32] and shows poorest photocatalytic degradation of dyes[33]. Based on above consideration, we constructed an efficient heterojunction photocatalyst for degradation of hazardous water pollutants which consisted of MXene sheets and ZnO. These heterojunctions facilitate minimize the photogenerated electron transfer distance. Moreover, the heterojunction structure between the stable ZnO and high conductive layered structure of $Ti_3C_2T_x$, MXene can further facilitate the separation and transfer capacities of photogenerated charge carriers. Therefore $ZnO/Ti_3C_2T_x$ exhibited excellent photocatalyst. This work provides new insight

into for development of traditional semiconductor photocatalyst for traditional semiconductor photocatalyst for highly efficient degradation of Rhodamine B as waste water pollutants.

Fig 1.) Schematical representation of Crystal Structure of Ti_3AlC_2 and monolayer of Ti_3C_2

2.Experimental Section

Etching Methods. Etching using NaF + HCl Solutions The etchant was prepared by adding 0.8 gm of NaF to 10 mL of 9M HCl and continuously stirring the resulting mixture for 10 min then 0.5 g of Ti_3AlC_2 powder gradually over the course of 5 min added into above etchants avoids excessive bubble formation of H_2 gas, and resultant mixture were left under continuous stirring for 18 h at room temperature. Each reactant was centrifugation with DI water until pH~6.

Synthesis of ZnO/MXene composite 110 mg $Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were dissolved into 50 ml of ethanol under vigorous stirring for 30 min at room temperature. Then 32 mg NaOH were dissolved into 50 mL of ethanol under vigorous stirring for 30 min, the two solutions were mixed followed by addition of the 410 mL of ethanol. 0.25 gm of MXene was added in the solution under magnetic stirring at $60^\circ C$ for 40 min. The resulting precipitate was cooled down and sediment was collected by centrifugation. Finally, the precipitate was dried at $60^\circ C$ in autoclave for 18 h obtained as ZnO seeds/MXene

37.10 g $Zn(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ and obtained ZnO/MXene were dissolved into 500 mL of DI Water in round bottom Flask, heated in oil bath at $105^\circ C$ for 30 min. Then, 17.50g

hexamethylenetetramine was added heated and stirred for 23h. Finally, after the reaction, process, the product was collected by centrifugation and dried in hot air oven at 60⁰C for 10 h

XRD of 2-D MXene:- The result revealed that the characteristics 002 peak located at $2\theta=8.83A^0$ In bare MXene, the 002 peak was found to be at $19A^0$ presenting as increase interlayer spacing this peak not appear into bulk counter part of MAX phases

Fig 2) XRD image of Ti₃C₂ 2-D Sheets

3. Photocatalytical Application of ZnO/MXene composite

The Photocatalytical performance were evaluated through removal of Rhodamine B as typical pollutants 200 mg ZnO/MXene composites were dispersed into 40 ml of 50 ppm solution of Rhodamine B, uniformed stirring with help of magnetic stirring. The solution kept in dark for 30 min and then irradiated with UV light for 18 min the reaction sample were collected at regular of 3 min for UV-visible analysis. The same set of experiment carried using 100 mg of ZnO particle were used to evaluated photocatalytical performance and the rhodamine b solution were collected at regular interval of 20 min for UV-Visible analysis

The degradation efficiency was evaluated by comparing percentage of degradation using following formula

$\eta = (1 - C_t/C_0)$ where η is photodegradation in % and C and C₀ are concentration of RhB solution after and before UV radiation, respectively. C/C₀ calculated by A/A₀, because the concentration of solution is directly proportion to absorbance of solution

Fig 3a) Photo catalytical degradation of Rhodamine B under UV light3b) Photodegradation efficiency of ZnO/MXene upto 5th cycle runs

Fig 4) comparison of photocatalytic degradation of Rhodamine B using ZnO andZnO/MXene

4. Conclusion: -In summary, ZnO/MXene composite have fabricated by two step facile chemical methods. The ZnO microrod/MXene composite within 15 min and more photocatalytical efficiency after 7cycles. ZnO/MXene composite is superior photocatalyst as compared to ZnO microrods. Therefore, the study opens new avenue for waste water pollutants and environmental protection.

5. Reference

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